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CONTROLLED STRAIN RESONANCE FREQUENCY FATIGUE TEST BENCH FOR CFRP

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FATIGUE TEST BENCH FOR CFRP

Carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRP) utilization enables to meet the requirements regarding stiffness, damping, and light weight for enhanced performance of machine tools. High-speed stamping presses, like the BRUDERER BSTA need to keep up with increasing customer demands regarding an increase of both quality and quantity of the delivered parts. Being among the quickest presses currently present on the market, these BSTA presses can reach speeds up to 2000 strokes per minute (spm) with a stroke of 8 mm, while guaranteeing a lifetime of 20000 hours at such speeds.

Stamping presses are expected to function for at least 1 billion cycles between maintenance intervals, which calls for great fatigue behavior of the employed materials. The cast iron ram of a BRUDERER BSTA-200 was redesigned in CFRP and the fatigue behavior of CFRP had to be tested in the very high cycle fatigue (VHCF) range. This was carried out with a newly developed controlled strain resonance frequency fatigue test bench. In order to complete 10^9 cycles within a couple of weeks, the testing occurred at the specimen's resonance frequency with a constant and controlled strain of 0.1%. The tested specimens are cylindrical, and the arrangement of the fibers was unidimensional (UD) – 0° and 90° .

Resonance frequency test bench

Hardware and software to control the test bench

CFRP utilization for the ram of a BRUDERER BSTA-200 high speed stamping press

